

INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Normurodov Bakhrom Khayrullayevich

Termez State University Faculty of Foreign

Philology Philology and language teaching: English 3rd year student.

Qodirova Mukaddas Tog'ayevna

Scientific adviser: Termez State University Faculty of Foreign

Philology Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

Abstract. In this article highlighted the different innovative and interesting of methods of teaching English. This paper shows the use of innovative techniques for teaching English communication skills to learners. Novel methods such audio video aids, games, group discussions, role play, brain storm will provide an easy way for learning the English communication skill and increase the confidence of the learners. This article characterizes combining two types which are traditional and modern methods of teaching and how we can make our teaching very effectively.

Key words: Innovative, innovation, traditional, modern, methods, role play, brainstorming, learning by doing, project training, traditional, modern.

Introduction.

A foreign language today is not just a part of the culture of a certain nation, but it is also the key to success, a successful future career for students. Achieving a high level of foreign language proficiency is impossible without fundamental language training in higher education. In most universities of the country, students master at least two foreign languages. It is important for a teacher to know the latest methods of teaching a foreign language, special teaching techniques and techniques in order to optimally select one or another teaching method in accordance with the level of knowledge, needs, and interests of students. After all, teaching methods are not what simple "algorithmic units", their rational and motivated use in foreign language lessons requires a creative approach on the part of the teacher, because "pedagogy is a science and art at the same time, therefore, the approach to choosing teaching methods should be based on the creativity of the teacher" 1. The purpose of this article is to review current trends in the development of foreign language teaching methods in higher education.

What do scientists invest in the concept of "method"? Teaching methods are "ordered methods of activity of the teacher and students aimed at the effective development of the obligations of educational and educational tasks". The method of teaching is "a tool of the teacher's activity to perform the leading function - teaching". The implementation of the teaching method is carried out through the use of a number of teaching methods, various approaches and working techniques. "Teaching methods are a set of specific learning situations that contribute to the achievement of an intermediate goal of a particular method" 4+ . The teaching of foreign languages are done traditional or slightly teacher-centered methods rather than modern student- centered applications and techniques while the transmission of knowledge and information has been realized with the usual form of lectures or discussions requiring physical presence of both student and the teacher. Furthermore the teaching methods used may differ in terms of the degree of influence on active learning. The aim of this article is to analyze the traditional and innovative methods for teaching and learning the foreign language as well as to reveal and prove a set of effective pedagogical conditions for learning languages.

However, traditional methodology is based largely on a reduction of the integrated process of using a foreign language. Very typical feature of traditional methodology is the teacher-dominated interaction. The teaching is deeply teacher-centered [3]. Unlike traditional methodology, modern methodology is much more student-centered. The teacher's main role is to help learning to happen, which includes involving students in what is going on by enabling them to work at their own speed, by not giving long explanations, by encouraging them to participate, talk, interact, and do things [2]. Broughton adds that the language student is best motivated by practice in which he senses the language is truly communicative that it is appropriate to its context, that his teacher's skills are moving him forward to a fuller competence in a foreign language [1].

Unfortunately, in teaching practice, foreign language teachers often use time-tested standard teaching methods. Sometimes the process of language teaching, regrettably, continues to be a "somewhat modernized version" of the grammar-translation method. The requirements for a foreign language lesson change over time, the latest teaching methods are being developed. At the present stage of development of science in Uzbekistan, one can definitely say that the times when the ability to translate adapted, non-authentic texts from a foreign language and vice versa have already passed. Today, the educational process in the universities of Uzbekistan is being reformed in accordance with the pan-European requirements for the quality of education: informatization of the educational space, integration processes in modern domestic education, establishing cooperation between universities and European educational institutions in the field of educational and scientific activities, student international exchanges, the possibility of obtaining a second higher education and training in master's programs abroad. In the conditions of reforming higher education, educational technologies for teaching foreign languages should also change. Language education itself is also gradually being modernized through the introduction of a modular-rating system for teaching foreign languages, interdisciplinary integration, democratization and economization of education brings to life innovations in the teaching of foreign languages. All this puts new requirements for teaching and teaching a foreign language in universities.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language in higher education at the present stage is to master students' communicative competencies, which will allow them to realize their knowledge, skills and abilities to solve specific communicative tasks in real life situations. A foreign language acts as a means of communication, communication with representatives of other nations, so that in education the culturological or intercultural approach to teaching continues to develop in the future within the framework of the concept of "dialogue of cultures", with the aim of forming students' polymer literacy. So, in my opinion, in a modern university there should be no place for such processes as memorization, thoughtless memorization of texts in a foreign language, which have no practical value for the future life of students. Students should be prepared on the basis of high-quality modern authentic educational material for the conscious use of a foreign language in later life and work. After all, a good knowledge of foreign languages now and will continue to be one of the leading requirements of employers in the future.

In this regard, it is the universities that are responsible for the quality provision of students with a set of language knowledge, skills, and this requires, first of all, the educational institution to systematically create conditions for the improvement of the qualifications of its teaching staff, to ensure the institution of proper material-technical base. High-quality language training of students is impossible without the use of modern educational technologies. Modern technologies in education are professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language, employment in teaching, the use of information and telecommunication technologies, working with educational computer

programs in foreign languages, distance technologies in teaching foreign languages, creating presentations in PowerPoint, using Internet resources, learning a foreign language in a computer environment (forums, blogs, e-mail), the latest test technologies (creating a bank of diagnostic materials for the course of the subject "Foreign Language" for conducting computer testing in order to control students' knowledge of learning) [5].

Research methodology. At this stage of the development of methodological science, the main methods of teaching foreign languages are communicative and constructive methods. Communicative method. Learning goal: mastering communicative competence. Learning content: texts should show conflicts that encourage the student to express their own opinion. Learning management: is not carried out through grammar, but is directed by communicative intentions. The student is at the center of learning. Language plane: the dominance of language production over language correctness, correctness, mistakes are allowed. Language becomes a means of communication. Exercises: exercises of the communicative direction. Students learn "communication in the process of communication itself. Therefore, all exercises and tasks must be communicatively justified by the lack of information, choice and reaction. Advantages of the method: students improve their oral speech skills, the fear of mistakes is overcome. Disadvantages of the method: due attention is not given to the quality of the language, communicative competence quickly reaches its limits. Constructive method. Learning goal: the method is based on the actual active learning of students. The task of the teacher is not to teach, but to facilitate the learning process. The lesson is action oriented. Educational content: proximity to reality of students, students are encouraged to independently construct their knowledge. Language plane: as wide as possible. Exercise: Language production is at the center of learning. Advantages of the method: preparing students for real life, real life situations.

Disadvantages of the method: at the present stage, they have not yet manifested themselves clearly enough. An example of a constructivist method is project-based learning. The methodology distinguishes between traditional and alternative teaching methods. Under the concept of alternative methods, a number of different approaches, techniques, and ways of transmitting a language are grouped. There are such alternative methods as the Total Physical Response method, the suggestive method, the dramatic pedagogical method, the silent method, the group method [4]. Innovative teaching methods include: computer-assisted learning (CALL), scenario method (story line method), simulation method, carousel method, station learning method, group puzzle method, roleplaying method, case study method (work over problem situations, students consider the problem, analyze the situation, present their ideas and options for solving the problem during the discussion). Scenario method (story line method). This method is based on the combination of planned educational meanings - for example, shops-products-sales - with the interests and ideas of students. By receiving "impulses" from the teacher, students contribute to the creation of history. This method dispenses with text tutorials. We are talking about creative planning, selection of a hypothesis, experiences, systematization and presentation of the work. The designed story also contains elements from drama and role-playing. The teacher only sets the framework for the action and presents individual episodes. Students ask their own questions and find their own answers. Project training. A learning technique in which students work on learning material that is organized into stations (students receive work plans with mandatory and optional tasks).

When learning by station, students have the opportunity to choose the distribution of time, the sequence of tasks and social forms used (individual work, pair work, group work). Thus, when using this method, students learn to plan their time, learn self-assessment, analyze their own

academic success, plan and conduct stages of work. Work on stations allows for differentiation according to the abilities, interests of students, according to the degree of complexity of the task. Simulation method. Especially in teaching a foreign language to students of economic specialties of universities, the simulation method can be successfully applied. In cybernetics, this term is used to model and simulate reality.

In training, we are talking about various simulation business games that provide students with the opportunity to develop their skills, apply knowledge in order to solve a particular problem in the so-called "safe environment", which simulates real situations, for example, in business, in work in a company. The simulation provides an opportunity for students to try themselves in a certain role - the head, the president of the company, gives the opportunity to explore the system of work of this enterprise. The participants in the game are given certain tasks - to achieve an increase in the company's profit, to conclude an agreement, to profitably sell the company's shares, and the like. Brainstorming method. The brainstorming method allows you to consider a variety of ideas: all participants discuss and prove their working hypothesis, supporting it with arguments. Ultimately, the "brainstorming" takes a collective solution to the problem, taken from a real situation or invented. Thus, the use of "brainstorming" allows students to gain useful managerial and organizational experience[7].

Of great interest and effective results is the method of working with Internet resources:

1. "List of links" ("Hotlist"): a list of annotated Internet resources on the topic under study.
2. "Multimedia Scrapbook" -studying a collection of multimedia links (photos, maps, stories, facts, quotes, audio clips, video fragments), selecting the necessary resource and creating your own collection of multimedia materials.
3. "Treasure Hunt" - the search for information that allows you to answer questions of a specific nature on the topic under study; implies the presence of problematic issues on the content of sites and the final task. [8].

Thus, the use of a variety of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages has a number of advantages that help teach students to actively acquire new knowledge, develop their creative and organizational skills, and give a powerful incentive to learn the language. Innovative technologies make it possible to perfectly combine theory with practice, form knowledge on the subject, professional skills and abilities. Conclusion: To conclude it should be noted that, the teacher of 21st century should shed traditional concepts and techniques of classroom teaching and should adopt the recent and innovative teaching techniques. English communication skill teachers must be innovative, creative and resourceful with thorough knowledge of the subject and adopt new techniques to change social economic status of our country. Whatever may be the methods and approaches, the most pragmatic and the desirable thing seems to explore the possibility of using the under used and valuable materials which will definitely facilitate the learning and teaching of language skills.

As well as, the use of a variety of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages has a number of advantages that help teach students to actively acquire new knowledge, develop their creative and organizational skills, and give a powerful incentive to learn the language. Innovative technologies make it possible to perfectly combine theory with practice, form knowledge on the subject, professional skills and abilities. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of multimedia technology and the spawning of a technologically-savvy generation of youths [9].

References:

1. Broughton G. Teaching English as a Foreign Language. Oxford university press, 2008
2. Scrivener J. Learning Teaching.- Oxford. Macmillan, 2005.
3. Mata K. ESL: Language Teaching Approaches.-Gata Review, 2001.
4. Volkova N. P. Pedagogy: Proc. allowance. — M.: Akademvidav, 2007. — 616 p. Kuzminsky A. I., Omelyanenko V. L. Pedagogy: Textbook. — M.: Znanie-Press, 2008. — 447 p. Methods of teaching foreign languages in secondary schools: Textbook / kol. authors under supervision. S. Yu. Nikolaeva. — M.: Lenvit, 1999. —320 p.
5. Boltaeva M. L. Business game in learning [Text] / M. L. Boltaeva // Young scientist. - 2012. - No. 2. - S. 252–254.
6. Tatarinova M. A. Pedagogical technologies for teaching foreign languages using web technologies.
7. Patil chetan Vitthal, Bhavna R Sharma, M. Ramachandran. Innovation Practices for Teaching English Communication skills to Professional Students - 2395-4396. Vol. 1 Issue-2 2015.